

188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science - Exercise 2

Assessing the Reproducibility of a Published Paper

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CCS Concepts: • **Reproducibility Experiment** → **Hyperparameter Tuning**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Experiment Replication, Recommender Systems, Hyperparameter Tuning, Machine Learning Models, Data Science

Abstract

Reproducing the results of a research paper can be challenging, as it requires ensuring that the code, datasets, and setup are consistent with the original study. Careful comparison of the reproduced results with those reported in the paper is essential to identify any significant differences. In this paper, we attempt to replicate the experiments from a selected study as part of the second exercise in the Experiment Design for Data Science lecture, aiming to understand and address potential issues in reproducibility.¹

1 Introduction

As part of the Experiment Design for Data Science course, we undertook the task of reproducing the results of the paper “*Everyone’s a Winner! On Hyperparameter Tuning of Recommendation Models*” by Faisal Shehzad and Dietmar Jannach. This paper critically examines the role of hyperparameter tuning in recommender systems, arguing that many studies fail to properly tune baseline models, leading to inflated claims of superiority for newly proposed algorithms. By systematically tuning a range of deep learning-based recommendation models, the authors demonstrate that even simple models can outperform more complex ones when properly tuned.

Our objective was to replicate the experiments described in the paper, assess the reproducibility of the results, and identify any challenges or discrepancies encountered during the process. Through this exercise, we aimed to contribute to the ongoing discussion on reproducibility in machine learning research and highlight the importance of transparent and well-documented experimental setups.

2 Paper Summary

This study examines the impact of hyperparameter tuning in recommender systems, exposing flaws in how new algorithms are evaluated. Experiments with seven deep learning models show that properly tuned models significantly outperform non-tuned ones, questioning many reported advancements. Additionally, simpler models like EASER and user-based KNN can rival or surpass deep learning models when tuned, challenging the notion that complex models always perform better.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14782576>

Using Tree Parzen Estimators, models were tuned for learning rates (0.0001–0.01), embedding dimensions (64, 128, 256), and iterations (10–50), optimizing for NDCG. Even the weakest tuned model outperformed the best non-tuned one, emphasizing the benefits of systematic tuning.

The paper concludes with a demand for better research procedures, such as mandatory reporting of hyperparameter tuning, expanding use of reproducible frameworks, and a more diversified set of baseline models. By implementing these guidelines, the recommender system community can ensure more equitable comparisons and meaningful progress in algorithm development. [2]

3 Strategies for Reproducing the Results

One of the key aspects of our work was ensuring the reproducibility of the results reported in *Everyone’s a Winner! On Hyperparameter Tuning of Recommendation Models*. To achieve this, we closely followed the setup outlined in the authors’ GitHub repository, verifying the correctness and functionality of their provided code.

3.1 Running the Provided Code

The original repository’s code ² runs flawlessly when executed according to the steps in the README .md file. The authors provided clear installation instructions, dataset links, and configuration files, making it straightforward to reproduce their experiments. We ensured that all necessary dependencies were installed within a dedicated virtual environment to avoid compatibility issues.

To maintain transparency and extend the reproducibility of our work, we are adding two supplementary Jupyter notebooks to the repository:

- **Preprocessing Notebook:** Documents the preprocessing steps before feeding the data into the models.
- **T-Test Notebook:** Contains the statistical tests we performed to validate the reported differences in model performance.

These additions enhance clarity, particularly regarding data preparation and statistical evaluation.

3.2 The Elliot Framework

The **Elliot framework** serves as the backbone of the experimental setup. It is a Python-based recommendation system evaluation tool that integrates multiple state-of-the-art models, hyperparameter tuning mechanisms, and evaluation protocols. One of its core advantages is that it allows experiments to be defined through configuration files, ensuring standardized and reproducible benchmarking.

Elliot automates the training and evaluation of various models while offering built-in support for hyperparameter tuning. It optimizes model parameters using techniques such as **Tree Parzen Estimators**, a Bayesian optimization method that efficiently searches for the best-performing hyperparameters.

3.3 Preprocessing and Experiment Execution

To manage the computational demands of training deep learning-based recommendation models, we had to make several adjustments:

- Instead of running all models simultaneously, we **processed each dataset separately** on different PCs to distribute the workload.
- Given the high runtime requirements, in some cases, we **ran one model at a time** to reduce memory usage and ensure stable execution.
- When faced with exceptionally long training times, we **reduced the number of epochs**, ensuring a balance between efficiency and model convergence.

²https://github.com/Faisalse/RecSys2023_hyperparameter_tuning/tree/master

3.4 Running the Code in a Virtual Environment

To ensure a controlled and reproducible software environment, we used **virtual environments** to isolate package dependencies. The following steps were followed:

- (1) We created a dedicated **conda environment** with the required dependencies as listed in the `README.md` file.
- (2) We activated the environment before running any scripts to ensure compatibility.
- (3) We followed the step-by-step execution process from the repository, running the tuned and untuned models separately.

This approach minimized version conflicts and ensured that all required libraries were properly installed.

3.5 Understanding Epochs in Model Training

An **epoch** represents one complete pass of the entire dataset through a machine learning model during training. In deep learning-based recommender systems, models adjust their internal weights across multiple epochs to minimize error and improve accuracy.

- Typically, a higher number of epochs allows the model to learn better representations, but excessive epochs may lead to **overfitting**.
- In our case, due to **runtime constraints**, we adjusted the number of epochs, particularly for resource-intensive models.
- As observed in our experiments, reducing the number of epochs did not significantly impact the model's final performance in most cases.

3.6 Additional Considerations

Beyond technical execution, we also took steps to ensure the **fair comparison** of tuned vs. untuned models. We strictly adhered to the original experiment's methodology, maintaining the same dataset splits, evaluation metrics (e.g., NDCG@10), and model selection process.

Furthermore, we validated our results against those reported in the original paper. The minor discrepancies observed in some cases (such as ConvMF on the Epinions dataset) were likely due to slight variations in training procedures, but overall, our findings align closely with the reported results.

By following a structured and methodical approach, we were able to successfully replicate the experiments while optimizing for practical constraints. Our additional contributions (preprocessing and statistical validation) provide further insight into the reproducibility of recommender system evaluations.

3.7 Supplementary Notebooks: Understanding and Validating the Data

While the original GitHub repository provides built-in preprocessing as part of its pipeline, we wanted to gain a deeper understanding of the data we were working with. To achieve this, we conducted our own preprocessing separately and documented the steps in an additional notebook.

To complement the existing implementation, we provide two supplementary Jupyter notebooks:

- **Preprocessing Notebook:** Although preprocessing is already handled within the GitHub code, we performed additional preprocessing ourselves to better explore the dataset and verify its structure.
- **T-Test Notebook:** To statistically confirm the significance of the performance differences between tuned and untuned models, we conducted a t-test analysis.

By incorporating these additional notebooks, we aimed to strengthen our comprehension of the dataset and ensure that our experimental setup remains transparent and well-documented.

4 Difficulties in Reproducing the Results

Reproducing the experiments from "Everyone’s a Winner! On Hyperparameter Tuning of Recommendation Models" presented several challenges, primarily due to the computational demands of the Elliot framework and inconsistencies in the provided code. Below, we outline the key difficulties we encountered and the steps we took to address them.

4.1 Computational Challenges with the Elliot Framework

The experiments were conducted using the Elliot framework, a Python-based tool for evaluating recommendation systems. While Elliot is a powerful and flexible framework, it is designed to run on CPU, which significantly increased the computational time for training and evaluating the models. To manage this, we made several adjustments:

To distribute the workload and reduce memory usage, we modified the configuration files to run one model at a time instead of running all models simultaneously.

When we further reduced the number of epochs for some of the more resource-intensive models, this adjustment allowed us to complete the experiments within a reasonable timeframe. It may have introduced minor discrepancies in the results, particularly for models that require extended training to converge fully.

4.2 Missing Code for the MostPop Method

The MostPop (Most Popular) method is a simple baseline recommendation algorithm that suggests the most popular items to users based on overall item popularity. Although the method is mentioned in the paper and included in the performance tables, the corresponding code was not provided in the repository. This omission prevented us from replicating the results for MostPop, which is a critical limitation given its role as a baseline model in the study.

5 Final Results

In this section, we compare our results with those from the original paper, identify inconsistencies, and interpret the results of the statistical tests.

Table 1. Tuned and Non-Tuned Models Performance (nDCG@10) from the paper [2]

Tuned Models	ML-1M		AMZm		Epinions	
	Model	nDCG@10	Model	nDCG@10	Model	nDCG@10
Multi-DAE	0.300	NeuMF	0.056	Multi-VAE	0.149	
Multi-VAE	0.294	Multi-VAE	0.054	Multi-DAE	0.146	
GMF	0.280	GMF	0.051	GMF	0.128	
NeuMF	0.277	Multi-DAE	0.048	NeuMF	0.118	
ONCF	0.225	MostPop	0.013	ONCF	0.077	
MostPop	0.162	ConvMF	0.011	MostPop	0.045	
ConvMF	0.160	NGCF	0.008	ConvMF	0.043	
NGCF	0.100	ONCF	0.009	NGCF	0.031	
Non-Tuned Models						
Multi-DAE	0.071	Multi-DAE	0.003	Multi-DAE	0.015	
ONCF	0.037	Multi-VAE	0.002	ONCF	0.005	
ConvMF	0.022	ConvMF	0.002	NGCF	0.003	
NeuMF	0.021	GMF	0.0007	GMF	0.002	
GMF	0.016	NGCF	0.0006	Multi-VAE	0.002	
NGCF	0.013	ONCF	0.0004	NeuMF	0.0008	
Multi-VAE	0.006	NeuMF	0.0004	ConvMF	0.0008	

5.1 Inconsistencies Between the Paper and the Source Code

The $EASE_R$ model’s performance values are provided only for the **tuned version**, with **NDCG@10 scores of 0.343 for ML-1M, 0.086 for AMZm, and 0.164 for Epinions**. However, the **untuned**

Table 2. Performance of Reproduced Tuned and Non-Tuned Models (nDCG@10). Values highlighted in red indicate models trained with fewer epochs.

Tuned Models	ML-1M		AMZm		Epinions	
	Model	nDCG@10	Model	nDCG@10	Model	nDCG@10
Mult-DAE	0.29256		NeuMF	0.02036	Mult-VAE	0.13184
Mult-VAE	0.15790		Mult-VAE	0.03306	Mult-DAE	0.02137
GMF	0.16011		GMF	0.00378	GMF	0.07170
NeuMF	0.20080		Mult-DAE	0.05645	NeuMF	0.11329
ONCF	0.17764		MostPop	N/A	ONCF	0.04642
MostPop	N/A		ConvMF	0.01191	MostPop	N/A
ConvMF	0.16009		NGCF	0.00236	ConvMF	0.03548
NGCF	0.07800		ONCF	0.00091	NGCF	0.01500
EASER	0.33366		EASER	0.08327	EASER	0.11751
Non-Tuned Models						
Mult-DAE	0.06770		Mult-DAE	0.00225	Mult-DAE	0.02000
ONCF	0.03200		Mult-VAE	0.000346	ONCF	0.00680
ConvMF	0.02528		ConvMF	0.000400	NGCF	0.00293
NeuMF	0.02160		GMF	0.000610	GMF	0.00180
GMF	0.01650		NGCF	0.000399	Mult-VAE	0.000810
NGCF	0.01240		ONCF	0.000781	NeuMF	0.00081095
Mult-VAE	0.02000		NeuMF	0.000181	ConvMF	0.000810

values are not reported, making it challenging to determine the actual impact of tuning in a direct tuned-vs-untuned comparison, despite the paper asserting its significance.

The authors claim that **EASER** would have outperformed all other tuned models across all datasets.[2] However, without the **untuned values**, it is difficult to draw a definitive conclusion regarding the effect of tuning on its performance.

Additionally, we found that the configuration for DMF (Deep Matrix Factorization) was included in the code for the tuned models, even though it was not mentioned in the paper. This inconsistency raises questions about whether DMF was originally considered in the reported experiments or if it was an undocumented addition in the shared implementation.

5.2 Statistical Comparison of Tuned and Non-Tuned Models

To evaluate the reproducibility of the reported results, we performed a paired t-test comparing the tuned models from the original paper with our reproduced results, which were obtained by rerunning the provided code. Statistical analysis was conducted in the file `t_test.ipynb` using Python's `scipy.stats.ttest_rel` function. This function computes the paired t-test using the formula[1]:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d/\sqrt{n}} \quad (1)$$

where: \bar{d} is the mean of the differences between the paired observations, s_d is the standard deviation of the differences, n is the number of paired observations.

A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) indicates a statistically significant difference between the original and reproduced results, suggesting that rerunning the code does not yield the same values. Conversely, a high p-value ($p \geq 0.05$) suggests that the differences may be due to random variation rather than a systematic issue.

5.3 Interpretation of the Results

The results indicate the following:

- For ML-1M (tuned models), the p-value (0.029) is below 0.05, suggesting a statistically significant difference between the original and reproduced values. This indicates that rerunning the model led to notable discrepancies, potentially due to differences in training conditions, such as hyperparameter

Table 3. Paired t-test results comparing the original and reproduced models.

Dataset	T-statistic	P-value
Tuned Models		
ML-1M	2.854	0.0290
AMZm	2.029	0.0888
Epinions	2.285	0.0624
Non-Tuned Models		
ML-1M	-0.578	0.5845
AMZm	2.000	0.0924
Epinions	-0.981	0.3645

variations or tuning methodologies.

- For AMZm and Epinions (tuned models), the p-values (0.0888 and 0.0624, respectively) are above 0.05, meaning the differences are not statistically significant but are still relatively close to the threshold. This suggests that while there are slight variations in results, they may not be substantial enough to conclude a lack of reproducibility.

- Non-tuned models do not show significant differences across any dataset, with all p-values well above 0.05.

The observed inconsistencies in the ML-1M dataset may be attributed to the reduced number of training epochs used during the experiments. Training a model for fewer epochs can lead to underfitting. While some models were trained with a reduced number of epochs, the majority were not, leaving questions regarding the reproducibility of the results. Additionally, we considered running the experiments with a reduced sample size to further test the reproducibility of the paper, however, this approach could have led to discrepancies between the original study and our reproduced results, as smaller sample sizes are known to increase variability and reduce the reliability of findings.

6 Conclusion

Although the paper provided a substantial foundation, certain aspects, such as the lack of details regarding the MostPop method and the lack of documented winning hyperparameters, made full replication more challenging. The omission of these details necessitated additional tuning efforts, which increased the complexity of the reproduction process. With these challenges, we believe that we were able to reproduce the results in an accurate way. Our tuning process gave results that were largely consistent with those reported, thus confirming the importance of careful hyperparameter selection can often perform competitively against more complex methods.

References

- [1] Douglas C. Montgomery and George C. Runger. 2010. *Applied Statistics and Probability for Engineers* (5 ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- [2] Faisal Shehzad and Dietmar Jannach. 2023. Everyone’s a Winner! On Hyperparameter Tuning of Recommendation Models. In *Proceedings of the Seventeenth ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys ’23)* (Singapore, Singapore). ACM, New York, NY, USA, 1–6. doi:10.1145/3604915.3609488